

Baker_et_al_Manuscript_Code

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Required Data

To run this script, please add the following files to your working directory:

- Baker_2022_All_Ambient_Loggers_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_PRISM_Precipitation_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Behavior_Delta_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Physiology_Delta_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Survival_Delta_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Behavior_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Physiology_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Survival_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Community_Data_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Experimental_Warming_Loggers_CSV.csv
- Baker_2022_Behavior_Loggers_CSV.csv
- Baker_2024_Vegetation_Warming_CSV.csv

Load Packages

```
## Loading required package: lme4
## Loading required package: Matrix
##
## Attaching package: 'lmerTest'
```

```
## The following object is masked from 'package:lme4':
##
##   lmer
## The following object is masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   step
## This is DHARMA 0.4.6. For overview type '?DHARMA'. For recent changes, type news(package = 'DHARMA')
```

Checking Versions

```
## [1] "DHARMA"
## [1] '0.4.6'
## [1] "lme4"
## [1] '1.1.31'
## [1] "lmerTest"
## [1] '3.1.3'
## [1] "MuMIn"
## [1] '1.48.4'
## [1] "R"
## [1] "R version 4.2.2 (2022-10-31)"
```

Mean Diel Temperature Stats Analysis Across Latitude

```
## [1] "Mean Diel Maximum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Latitude 0.31134 0.31134      1 5.8347  0.2413 0.6412
## [1] "Mean Diel Mean Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Latitude 0.18872 0.18872      1 6.0761  2.5131 0.1634
## [1] "Mean Diel Minimum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Latitude 0.042599 0.042599      1 6.0154   1.08 0.3387
## [1] "Mean Diel Range in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Latitude 0.21621 0.21621      1 6.1407  0.1433 0.7177
## [1] "Mean Diel Coefficient of Variation in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Latitude 0.20656 0.20656      1 6.1078  0.0758 0.7922
```

Mean Diel Temperature Stats Analysis Across Elevation

```
## [1] "Mean Diel Maximum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Elevation 0.19521 0.19521      1 5.6296  0.1521 0.7109
## [1] "Mean Diel Mean Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Elevation 0.030281 0.030281      1 5.9601  0.4038 0.5487
## [1] "Mean Diel Minimum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Elevation 0.038527 0.038527      1 5.9978  0.9767 0.3612
## [1] "Mean Diel Range in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Elevation 0.21876 0.21876      1 5.8554  0.145 0.7168
## [1] "Mean Diel Coefficient of Variation in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Elevation 0.49416 0.49416      1 5.9799  0.1813 0.6851
```

Site Type Designations

What Climate Variables Explain The Observed Variation in Grasshopper Plasticity

```
## boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')
##           Behavior Physiology Survival Solidago Grass
## Latitude 9.939687 8.605270 5.325071 6.4171892 1.665645
## Mean Diel Maximum 0.000000 0.000000 0.000000 0.0000000 4.860231
## Mean Diel Mean 9.626064 7.862191 5.949285 0.3684448 0.000000
## Mean Diel Minimum 5.906043 8.259119 8.393991 8.7142088 2.791878
## Mean Diel Coeff. of Var. 5.906043 8.259119 8.393991 8.7142088 2.791878
## Mean Diel Range 5.906043 8.259119 8.393991 8.7142088 2.791878
## Populations Ungrouped 5.240436 30.733084 10.197351 12.4869023 14.431006
## [1] "Grouping populations by mean diel maximum temperatures was the best model for behavioral plasticity"
```

Climate Data

Mean Diel Temperature Stats Among Site Types

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population is nested within Site Type)"
## [1] "Mean Diel Maximum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type 22.027 22.027      1 5.868 17.182 0.006343 **
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```

## [1] "Mean Diel Mean Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type 0.13022 0.13022      1 5.9725  1.7339 0.2362
## [1] "Mean Diel Minimum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq  Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type 0.0081763 0.0081763      1 6.004  0.2073 0.6649
## [1] "Mean Diel Range in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type 2.1866  2.1866      1 6.0375  1.4499 0.2736
## [1] "Mean Diel Coefficient of Variation in Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type 1.3182  1.3182      1 6.054  0.4837 0.5126

```

Precipitation Among Site Types

```

## [1] "Mean Diel Precipitation"
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Response: Precipitation
##           Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type  1 1.3302 1.33020  3.4806 0.1113
## Residuals  6 2.2930 0.38217

```

Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Temperature Stats

```

## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population o
## [1] "Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Maximum Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type      4.694  4.694      1    6  4.2523  0.08481 .
## Warming        62.233 62.233      1   22 56.3703 1.665e-07 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.306  0.306      1   22  0.2773  0.60374
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## [1] "Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Mean Temperature"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type      0.0386 0.0386      1    6  0.3900  0.5553
## Warming        3.5818 3.5818      1   22 36.2280 4.663e-06 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.2225 0.2225      1   22  2.2508  0.1478
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## [1] "Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Minimum Temperature"

```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    0.02118 0.02118     1     6  0.3546 0.573256
## Warming       0.57873 0.57873     1    22  9.6926 0.005065 **
## Site.Type:Warming 0.11623 0.11623     1    22  1.9466 0.176876
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
## [1] "Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Range in Temperature"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    0.834   0.834     1  6.0026  0.6495   0.4510
## Warming      74.814  74.814     1 21.9989 58.2543 1.278e-07 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.045   0.045     1 21.9989  0.0351   0.8531
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
## [1] "Influence of Experimental Warming on Mean Diel Coefficient of Variation"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    0.148   0.148     1     6  0.0526   0.8262
## Warming     160.003 160.003     1    22 56.8467 1.556e-07 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.252   0.252     1    22  0.0895   0.7676
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Influence of Experimental Warming on Temperature Stats During Behavioral Assays

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population
```

```
## [1] "Maximum Temperature During Behavioral Assays"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    3.11    3.11     1     6  1.8505   0.2226
## Warming     420.36  420.36     1    22 250.0659 1.69e-13 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 1.46    1.46     1    22  0.8698   0.3611
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
## [1] "Mean Temperature During Behavioral Assays"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    1.220   1.220     1     6  1.6219   0.2499
## Warming     287.497 287.497     1    22 382.3369 2.135e-15 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.335   0.335     1    22  0.4461   0.5111
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
## [1] "Minimum Temperature During Behavioral Assays"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    0.374   0.374     1     6  0.1822   0.6844
## Warming     80.233  80.233     1    22 39.0913 2.716e-06 ***
## Site.Type:Warming 0.021   0.021     1    22  0.0100   0.9213
```

```
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

## [1] "Range in Temperature During Behavioral Assays"

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##              Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value    Pr(>F)
## Site.Type      0.041   0.041     1     6  0.0097    0.9247
## Warming        133.294 133.294     1    22 31.6163 1.183e-05 ***
## Site.Type:Warming  1.136   1.136     1    22  0.2695    0.6088
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

## [1] "Coefficient of Variation in Temperature During Behavioral Assays"

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##              Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF DenDF F value    Pr(>F)
## Site.Type      4.0024  4.0024     1     6  0.5082  0.50268
## Warming        25.9633 25.9633     1    22  3.2969  0.08307 .
## Site.Type:Warming 10.4349 10.4349     1    22  1.3250  0.26205
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Behavioral Plasticity

Behavioral Plasticity Analysis

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
```

```
##              Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value   Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    2659.2  2659.2     1   5.860  6.7752 0.0413939 *
## Predation    5539.1  5539.1     1  52.948 14.1125 0.0004303 ***
## Site.Type:Predation 1679.0  1679.0     1  52.948  4.2778 0.0435128 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Physiological Plasticity

Physiological Plasticity Analysis

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population"
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"
```

DHARMA residual


```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##              Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value   Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    34.63   34.63     1   5.859  0.1003 0.76246
## Predation    95.98   95.98     1  52.481  0.2779 0.60027
## Temperature  356.16  178.08     2 116.000  0.5157 0.59846
## Site.Type:Predation 1742.39 1742.39     1  52.481  5.0455 0.02892 *
## Site.Type:Temperature 2116.79 1058.40     2 116.000  3.0649 0.05046 .
## Predation:Temperature  17.43    8.72     2 116.000  0.0252 0.97508
## Site.Type:Predation:Temperature 1130.37  565.18     2 116.000  1.6366 0.19910
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Plant Community Impacts

Solidago Biomass Analysis

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population c
## [1] "Check that there are no differences in initial percent cover of Solidago"

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF   DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Warming      22.004   22.004     1 146.005  0.9595 0.3289
## Site.Type    35.857   35.857     1   6.004  1.5636 0.2577
## Predation     1.235    1.235     1 146.187  0.0538 0.8168
## Warming:Site.Type 38.634   38.634     1 146.005  1.6847 0.1963
## Warming:Predation  0.097    0.097     1 146.187  0.0042 0.9483
## Site.Type:Predation 0.394    0.394     1 146.187  0.0172 0.8960
## Warming:Site.Type:Predation 1.213    1.213     1 146.187  0.0529 0.8184

## [1] "Confirmed no differences in initial percent cover of Solidago"
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF   DenDF F value  Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    0.67817  0.67817     1     6.00   7.1398 0.03693 *
## Warming      0.39801  0.39801     1 146.00   4.1902 0.04245 *
## Predation     0.01056  0.01056     1 146.04   0.1111 0.73932
## Site.Type:Warming 0.43283  0.43283     1 146.00   4.5569 0.03446 *
## Site.Type:Predation 0.00158  0.00158     1 146.04   0.0167 0.89744
## Warming:Predation  0.06869  0.06869     1 146.04   0.7232 0.39648
## Site.Type:Warming:Predation 0.00015  0.00015     1 146.04   0.0016 0.96820
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Grass Biomass Analysis

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population
```

```
## [1] "Check that there are no differences in initial percent cover of grass"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
```

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
Warming	378.53	378.53	1	145.999	1.5922	0.2090
Site.Type	0.34	0.34	1	5.999	0.0014	0.9713
Predation	56.88	56.88	1	146.018	0.2392	0.6255
Warming:Site.Type	112.45	112.45	1	145.999	0.4730	0.4927
Warming:Predation	41.42	41.42	1	146.018	0.1742	0.6770
Site.Type:Predation	337.43	337.43	1	146.018	1.4193	0.2355
Warming:Site.Type:Predation	9.26	9.26	1	146.018	0.0390	0.8438

```
## [1] "Confirmed no differences in initial percent cover of grass"
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
```

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
Site.Type	6.58	6.58	1	6.00	0.0235	0.88329
Warming	8.24	8.24	1	146.00	0.0294	0.86407
Predation	18.20	18.20	1	146.01	0.0650	0.79919
Site.Type:Warming	270.37	270.37	1	146.00	0.9647	0.32763
Site.Type:Predation	148.24	148.24	1	146.01	0.5290	0.46821
Warming:Predation	882.19	882.19	1	146.01	3.1477	0.07812
Site.Type:Warming:Predation	123.66	123.66	1	146.01	0.4412	0.50758

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Grasshopper Survival

Grasshopper Survival

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
```

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
## Site.Type	11334	11334	1	6.006	2.4606	0.167741
## Predation	1273	1273	1	70.273	0.2763	0.600775
## Site.Type:Predation	44565	44565	1	70.273	9.6749	0.002699 **

```
## ---
```

```
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Vegetation Control Experiment

Influence of experimental warming on Solidago Biomass

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"
```

```
## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
```

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
## Site.Type	0.186436	0.186436	1	4.025	2.6315	0.1796
## Warming	0.016147	0.016147	1	52.096	0.2279	0.6351
## Site.Type:Warming	0.001342	0.001342	1	52.096	0.0189	0.8911

```
## [1] "Confirmed there is no direct effect of experimental warming on Solidago biomass"
```

Influence of experimental warming on Grass Biomass

```
## [1] "Note Population is implicitly nested within Site Type as a random effect (i.e. each Population"
```

DHARMA residual


```
## [1] "Diagnostic plots look good proceed with analysis"

## Type III Analysis of Variance Table with Satterthwaite's method
##           Sum Sq Mean Sq NumDF  DenDF F value Pr(>F)
## Site.Type    134.03   134.03     1    3.993  0.2727 0.6291
## Warming       145.89   145.89     1   52.060  0.2969 0.5882
## Site.Type:Warming 636.67   636.67     1   52.060  1.2955 0.2602

## [1] "Confirmed there is no direct effect of experimental warming on grass biomass"
```